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Mapping Synergies and Trade-offs Among Climate Resilience Indicators: A Systematic Review Based Cross-Impact Framework for Buildings

Ashmin Aryal^{1†}, Shashwat Sinha¹, Brijesh Mainali¹, Krushna Mahapatra¹

¹ Linnaeus University, Faculty of Technology, Department of Built Environment and Energy Technology. Linnaeus University.

† Corresponding author, Email: ashmin.aryal@lnu.se

Abstract: With climate-driven disasters escalating in frequency and cost, advancing integrated resilience frameworks is urgently needed to safeguard the built environment. This study conducts a systematic literature review to identify and consolidate 31 building-level resilience indicators across five domains of climate-related risk and performance: flood, fire, wind, thermal, and energy. Pairwise interactions among indicators were assessed using a Cross-Impact Matrix (CIM), distinguishing synergies, trade-offs, neutral interdependencies, and unrelated connections. A network analysis was then applied, using out-degree and betweenness centrality to evaluate indicator influence and bridging capacity. Results show that building envelope- and structure-related measures, such as roof assembly resistance, roof pitch, roof geometry, and exterior door resistance, occupy central network positions, acting as core indicators with strong co-benefits. Gateways such as wall assembly and insulation link domains, while influencers like energy use for heating and cooling exert directional effects but may introduce trade-offs. Isolates, including backup power autonomy and stormwater-sewer separation, remain hazard-specific with limited systemic influence. By integrating matrix- and network-based approaches, this study provides an evidence-based framework for multi-hazard resilience planning, supporting more strategic building design and retrofitting.

Keywords: Resilience, buildings, synergy and trade-offs, climate change

Main highlights:

1. Indicators are refined to 31 resilience measures, analysed across flood, fire, wind, thermal, and energy domains.
2. Cross Impact Matrix revealed synergies, trade-offs, and neutral links.
3. Roof-related indicators had the highest synergy score across the system.
4. Energy use and lateral wall resistance showed most trade-offs across the system.

Institute for Sustainable Futures, De Montfort University, Leicester LE1 9BH, UK

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5. Wall assembly, insulation and window glazing are identified as key leverage points.

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Introduction

Climate change is intensifying the frequency and severity of environmental hazards such as extreme heat, flooding, wildfires, strong winds, and cold snaps (Miškić, Ćorić and Vukosavljević, 2017; Farahani et al., 2024). These climate-induced events exacerbate financial risks and increase the vulnerability of buildings, particularly during extreme weather conditions (CEA Insurers of Europe, 2013; Miskic, Coric and Vukosavljevic, 2017). The implications may be significant, as buildings are typically renovated only once or twice over their lifespan. Embedded resilience and adaptability considerations are crucial for buildings in all phases of their lifecycle to ensure long-term functionality and safety.

Initially described in relation to ecological systems, resilience is a system's ability to withstand shocks, adjust to disruptions, and preserve or restore its fundamental operations (Holling, 1973). Climate-resilient buildings are designed to stay strong, respond effectively, and recover from the impacts of changing climate conditions. More than just protecting the structure, they take a complete approach to reduce or prevent the negative effects of current and future climate challenges (European Union, 2023; Stamatopoulos et al., 2024). However, a key challenge lies in the limited integration of resilience within existing building codes and policy frameworks, where clear criteria and enforceable requirements are often absent. Even when resilience is acknowledged, critical elements such as hazard-specific adaptation and the management of compound risks are often underdeveloped. For instance, the European Union's Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) emphasizes decarbonization and indoor environmental quality but offers limited guidance on how buildings should be resilient to multiple or overlapping climate hazards (European Union, 2023; Bankert et al., 2024; UN Environment Programme & Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction, 2025). As a result, resilience is frequently treated as an optional or complementary feature, rather than a central regulatory requirement.

This concern is further amplified by the age and condition of Europe's building stock. Approximately 80 percent of the buildings that will be in use by 2050 already exist today, and around 75 percent of these are energy inefficient (JRC, 2021; Stamatopoulos et al., 2024). More than half of Europe's residential buildings were constructed before 1971, often with outdated materials, systems, and design standards that are ill-suited to current and future climate threats (CORDIS, 2014; Stamatopoulos et al., 2024).

Much of the existing literature and resilience efforts are narrow and hazard-specific. For example, some research has focused specifically on fire resilience (Manes, Lange and Rush, 2023; Zhang et al., 2023), while others have concentrated on flood resilience, thermal resilience (Miguez, Raupp and Veról, 2019; Cirrincione, Marvuglia and Scaccianoce, 2021; Hong et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2024; Hamidi, Novo and Paavola, 2025), and storm or wind-related resilience (Van De Lindt, Wang and Van De Lindt, 2020; Nofal et al., 2023). While these provide valuable insights, these hazard-specific studies often overlook the complex

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interactions and potential trade-offs between different resilience measures. For instance, airtightness can improve efficiency but raise overheating risks (Psomas et al., 2016; Baniassadi and Sailor, 2018; Morshed and Mourshed, 2023), while added insulation may improve thermal comfort but increase fire vulnerability depending on the insulation material (Farrokhirad et al., 2024). Such examples highlight the need for a systems-based, multi-hazard resilience strategy that accounts for synergies, conflicts, and cascading effects. This paper responds to these challenges by proposing a comprehensive, indicator-driven framework to support integrated resilience planning in the built environment.

Methodology

This study applies a structured, multi-phase methodology to identify, classify, and evaluate building-level resilience indicators across five domains: flood, fire, wind, thermal, and energy. Energy and thermal resilience are essential, as disasters can disrupt supply, impair comfort, and hinder recovery, while reliable energy and passive thermal performance reinforce building functionality and support hazard response across all domains. The approach combines a systematic literature review (SLR), a Cross-Impact Matrix (CIM), and Qualitative Network Analysis (QNA) to examine synergies, trade-offs, and interdependencies among resilience strategies. Cross-Impact Matrix (CIM), Qualitative Network analysis (Weitz et al., 2018; Mainali et al., 2018) is an established methodology used in synergy trade off analyses. Together, these steps inform the development of a comprehensive framework for multi-hazard resilience assessment in buildings.

While frameworks such as those of IPCC (IPCC, 2023), UNDRR's Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2015) recognize resilience across physical, social, economic, and institutional dimensions, this study focuses only on the physical dimension at the building level. Indicators that can be systematically assessed using engineering criteria, even when qualitative in nature are selected. Societal, institutional and economic aspects are acknowledged as important but remain outside the scope to ensure methodological clarity and actionable insights for building design. A systematic literature review was conducted in SCOPUS, the largest database of peer-reviewed articles (Aghaei Chadegani et al., 2013), following PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure transparency and reproducibility. A targeted search string combined keywords on building resilience and climate hazards, and the search was restricted to peer-reviewed journal articles in English. Studies were included if they focused on the built environment, addressed at least one of the five domains, and identified measurable indicators or design features for resilience. The screening process followed the PRISMA protocol, supported by the machine learning platform ASReview (van de Schoot et al., 2021), which applied active learning to prioritize relevant studies. Out of 1,276 retrieved records, 106 articles were included.

From the reviewed articles, a total of 994 resilience-related indicators were initially extracted. To make the analysis manageable and relevant for building-level application, this long list was systematically refined through several steps. First, duplicates and overlapping indicators were removed to avoid redundancy. Next, indicators that were too broad (e.g., community-level or regional-scale) or too narrow (e.g., highly context-specific measures with no wider applicability) were excluded. The remaining set was then normalized by consolidating similar

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indicators under common definitions (for example, different terms referring to roof design features were grouped into a single indicator). This refined pool was further filtered using a multi-criteria screening process that assessed indicators for relevance, measurability, uniqueness, cross-hazard applicability, and policy or stakeholder value. Only those that scored consistently high across these criteria were retained. Following this structured reduction process, the initial 994 indicators were consolidated into a final set of 31 unique, building-level resilience indicators (Table 1). Each indicator was then mapped to one or more hazard domains, and their interactions were examined using a CIM. Relationships were classified as synergistic (+1), conflicting (−1), inter-dependent (0), or not applicable (N). The CIM was then translated into a directed network model using Python, NetworkX (Hagberg, Schult and Swart, 2008)(Cao et al., 2023), where indicators were represented as nodes and relationships as edges. The network analysis used degree centrality to identify highly connected indicators and betweenness centrality to highlight bridging indicators that link clusters across hazard domains. Out-degree centrality is calculated using equation 1.

$$C_{out}(i) = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j} \omega_{ij}}{N-1} \quad (1)$$

where $\omega_{ij} = +1$ for a synergy, -1 for a trade-off, and 0 for an interdependency, and N is the total number of indicators. This reflects the direct influence of indicator i .

Betweenness centrality is calculated using equation 2.

$$C_B(i) = \sum_{s \neq i \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st(i)}}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{st} is the number of shortest paths between indicators s and t , and $\sigma_{st(i)}$ is the number of those paths passing through i . This reflects the extent to which indicator i bridges different parts of the network. Together, out-degree centrality highlights indicators with strong direct influence, while betweenness centrality identifies those mediating interactions.

Results

A total of 31 unique building-level resilience indicators were selected for the final analysis, cross five domains: flood, fire, wind, thermal, and energy (see Table 1).

Table 1: Building-level resilience indicators (I) grouped by hazard domain (detailed in Annex 1, Table A1).

Domain	Indicators
Fire	I01 Structural Fire Resistance Rating (FRR)
	I02 Active Fire Protection System Coverage
	I03 Wall Assembly Rating
	I07 External Shutter & Impact Protection
	I08 Ventilation System & Air Change Rate
	I18 Roof Assembly Multi-Hazard Resistance
Flood	I19 Exterior Door Fire–Flood–Wind Resistance
	I28 Primary Structural System Type
	I31 Defensible Space for fire Protection
I09 Stormwater–Sewer Separation	I21 Plinth/Base Level Elevation

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	I10 Drainage Network Capacity for Extreme Rainfall	I22 Foundation Type & Hazard Resistance
	I12 Flood-Safe Placement of Plumbing Fixtures	I23 Floodwater Removal System Capacity
	I17 Ground Floor Opening-to-Wall Ratio	I24 External Envelope Floodproofing Coverage
	I20 Elevation of Lowest Occupied Floor	I30 Gutter Guard & Debris Protection Coverage
		I19 Exterior Door
Thermal	I03 Wall Assembly Rating	I15 Unmet Degree Hours (UDH) for Thermal Comfort
	I04 In-Wall Insulation	I18 Roof Assembly Multi-Hazard Resistance
	I05 Window-to-Wall Ratio (WWR)	I25 Roof Geometry & Shape Performance
	I06 Window Glazing Energy Impact Rating	I26 Roof Pitch Angle
	I08 Ventilation System & Air Change Rate	I27 Roof Overhang Length for Shading & Rain Protection
	I13 Indoor Overheating Degree (IOD)	
	I14 Specific Energy Use for Heating & Cooling	
Wind	I05 Window-to-Wall Ratio (WWR)	I19 Exterior Door Fire
	I06 Window Glazing Energy-Impact Rating	I25 Roof Geometry & Shape Performance
	I07 External Shutter & Impact Protection	I26 Roof Pitch Angle
	I16 Structural Anchoring & Connection Compliance	I28 Primary Structural System Type
	I17 Ground Floor Opening-to-Wall Ratio	I29 Wall Lateral Load Resistance Capacity
	I18 Roof Assembly Multi-Hazard Resistance	
Energy	I03 Wall Assembly Rating	I11 Backup Power Autonomy for Critical Loads
	I04 In-Wall Insulation	
	I05 Window-to-Wall Ratio (WWR)	I14 Specific Energy Use for Heating & Cooling
	I06 Window Glazing Energy Impact Rating	

The CIM was then populated based on the relationships among indicators as synergistic, conflicting, or neutral as illustrated in Annex 1: Table A2.

Network Structure

Figure 1 is a network visualization of building-level resilience indicators. Each node (circle) represents one indicator (labelled I01–I31), and each edge (line) between nodes represents the type of relationship between two indicators. The edges are color-coded: green solid lines indicate synergies (+1), where improving one indicator supports another; red dashed lines indicate trade-offs (−1), where strengthening one indicator may weaken another; and gray dotted lines indicate interdependencies (0), where indicators are linked without clear positive or negative effects. Some nodes also have self-loops (lines that return to the same node),

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representing self-reinforcing or internal relationships. The network map reveals a densely connected system of 31 building-level resilience indicators, with synergies (green) more common than trade-offs (dotted red). Indicators linked to the building envelope, such as roof assembly resistance (I18), roof pitch (I26), and roof geometry (I25), demonstrate high connectivity, showing that they strongly influence the other measures across systems. Similarity structural measures important for flood and wind resilience, such as exterior door resistance (I19) and ground floor opening ratio (I17), also acted as important connectors, indicating their role as cross-domain co-benefit enablers. In contrast, more operational or hazard-specific indicators, such as stormwater–sewer separation (I09) and backup power autonomy (I11), show fewer connections, reflecting narrower but valuable functions. Because there are so many overlapping lines, it can be difficult to visualize how each indicator balances benefits and drawbacks. So, Figure 2 summarizes this information by showing the number of synergies (x-axis) and tradeoffs (y-axis) for each indicator. The two figures show that indicators such as I17, I19, I10, I11, I04, I09, I18, I07, I28, I29, I16, and I02 are the most connected in the network and influence many others. Among these, I18, I23, I28, I21, and I25 mostly create positive links, making them especially important for strengthening resilience. Some indicators like I19, I16, I02, and I01 are also very influential but create both positive and negative links, so they need to be applied with care. A smaller group, I14, I15, I13, and I05, create more negative than positive links, which means they could cause problems if not managed properly. Finally, indicators such as I12, I06, I03, I22, I24, I26, I27, I30, and I31 have fewer connections and play a more supportive role in the system.

Figure 1: Resilience Indicator Network

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Figure 2: Synergy vs Trade-off Quadrant

Centrality Analysis

To further understand the systemic role of each resilience indicator, centrality measures were applied to the network derived from the CIM with the results illustrated in Figure 3. Median cut-offs divide the plots into four quadrants, distinguishing indicators above or below average

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in influence and bridging capacity (see Figure 3). For example, indicator I18 shows an out-degree near 0.97 (29 of 30 possible links) and high betweenness (~0.010), making it both highly influential and a key bridge. In contrast, I12 has lower out-degree (~0.57) and near-zero betweenness, reflecting limited influence and no bridging role.

Figure 3: Resilience indicator centrality quadrant

This analysis shows core indicators (green) such as roof assembly resistance (I18), roof pitch (I26), roof geometry (I25), and exterior door resistance (I19) combine high out-degree with moderate betweenness, making them highly influential and integrative within the multi-hazard framework. Gateways (blue), including wall assembly (I03), in-wall insulation (I04), and window glazing (I06), exhibit relatively higher betweenness despite moderate out-degree, positioning them as connectors that link structural, thermal, and energy domains. Influencers (orange), such as energy use for heating and cooling (I14) and wall lateral resistance (I29), display high out-degree but low betweenness, reflecting strong directional influence with more limited bridging capacity. Finally, isolates (grey), such as structural fire resistance (I01), backup power autonomy (I11), or flood-safe plumbing (I12), score low on both measures, indicating specialized roles with limited systemic integration. Indicators located at the core are predominantly synergy-dominant and strongly interconnected, reinforcing their value as co-benefit levers in resilience planning. Gateways support cross-hazard integration by connecting thermal, energy, and wind-proof measures, while influencers demand careful management due to their trade-off potential. Isolates remain important within specific hazard contexts but do not substantially shape systemic resilience outcomes. Together, these results reveal a core bridge periphery structure in the indicator network: highly connected envelope and structural measures form the backbone of multi-hazard resilience, bridging indicators ensure integration across domains, and more peripheral indicators provide targeted hazard-specific protection.

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Conclusion

This study systematically identified and analyzed 31 unique building-level resilience indicators across five domains: flood, fire, wind, thermal, and energy. Through a structured review and consolidation process, indicators were evaluated not only for their relevance within individual hazard categories but also for their potential to contribute to integrated, multi-hazard resilience strategies. The synergy trade-off analysis demonstrated that most indicators are synergy-dominant, meaning they reinforce rather than undermine other resilience measures. Building envelopes and structural elements, such as roof assembly resistance, roof pitch, roof geometry, and exterior door resistance, emerged as co-benefit levers that strengthen performance across multiple hazards. At the same time, a small subset of indicators, including energy use for heating and cooling and wall lateral resistance capacity, revealed higher trade-off potential, underscoring the need for careful integration during retrofitting or new construction. Network analysis further highlighted the systemic structure of building resilience. Core indicators combined high influence and connectivity, forming the backbone of multi-hazard resilience. Gateway indicators served as bridges between domains, enabling cross-hazard integration. Influencers exerted strong directional effects but carried trade-off risks, while isolates played more specialized roles with limited systemic connectivity. Together, these results point to a core bridge periphery structure in building resilience, where central envelope and structural measures support system-wide robustness, complemented by bridging and specialist indicators that provide targeted hazard protection. The findings offer a systematically derived set of indicators that can guide resilience assessments, policy frameworks, and practical design strategies, suggesting that prioritizing core and gateway indicators will deliver the greatest resilience benefits, while influencers and isolates require tailored management to avoid unintended consequences.

This study identified and analyzed 31 building-level indicators of resilience across five domains: flood, fire, wind, thermal, and energy. The results show that many indicators provide multi-hazard co-benefits, with building envelopes and structural features such as roof design, wall assembly, insulation, and window glazing emerging as the most influential. These act as leverage points because improvements in them enhance performance against several hazards at once. A smaller group of indicators, such as energy use for heating and cooling or wall lateral resistance, showed trade-off potential, meaning they may strengthen resilience against one hazard but create vulnerabilities in another if not carefully integrated.

The synergy trade-off analysis is therefore essential for decision-making: it shows where measures can be combined for maximum co-benefits (synergies), and where caution is needed to avoid negative side effects (trade-offs). This interpretation directly supports the development of a composite resilience indicator, since it clarifies which measures should be weighted more heavily and how to balance competing effects when assessing overall resilience. Resilience strategies should prioritize core indicators (like Roof Assembly Multi-Hazard Resistance (I18), roof pitch (I26), roof geometry (I25)) and exterior door resistance (I19)) gateway indicators (like wall assembly (I03), in-wall insulation (I04), and window glazing (I06)) to maximize benefits across hazards, while using the insights from the synergy–trade-off analysis to guide how influencers and isolates are applied in practice.

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For future work, the refined indicator set, and the synergy trade-off relationships will be validated with empirical data and case studies. This validated framework will then form the basis of a composite indicator for assessing building resilience across domains, offering policymakers, designers, and practitioners a reliable and practical tool for resilience planning and retrofitting.

Reference

- AGHAEI CHADEGANI, A. et al. (2013) A comparison between two main academic literature collections: Web of science and scopus databases. *Asian Social Science*, 9(5), pp. 18–26.
- BANIASSADI, A. and SAILOR, D.J. (2018) Synergies and trade-offs between energy efficiency and resiliency to extreme heat – A case study. *Building and Environment*, 132, pp. 263–272.
- BANKERT, E. et al. (2024) *TOWARDS A CLIMATE-RESILIENT BUILT ENVIRONMENT*.
- CAO, M. et al. (2023) Spatio-temporal changes in the causal interactions among Sustainable Development Goals in China. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01952-z.
- CEA INSURERS OF EUROPE (2013) *Tackling climate change: The vital contribution of insurers*.
- CIRRINCIONE, L., MARVUGLIA, A. and SCACCIANOCE, G. (2021) Assessing the effectiveness of green roofs in enhancing the energy and indoor comfort resilience of urban buildings to climate change: Methodology proposal and application. *Building and Environment*, 205, [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.108198.
- CORDIS (2014) *Europe's building stock – A comprehensive study*. [Online] <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/138853-europes-building-stock-a-comprehensive-study>.
- FARAHANI, A.V. et al. (2024) Hot Summers in Nordic Apartments: Exploring the Correlation between Outdoor Weather Conditions and Indoor Temperature. *Buildings*, 14(4), [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.3390/buildings14041053.
- FARROKHIRAD, E. et al. (2024).
- GUO, J. et al. (2024) Assessing the winter indoor environment with different comfort metrics in self-built houses of hot-humid areas: Does undercooling matter for the elderly? *Building and Environment*, 263, [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111871.
- HAGBERG, A.A., SCHULT, D.A. and SWART, P.J. (2008) *Exploring Network Structure, Dynamics, and Function using NetworkX*.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- HAMIDI, A.R., NOVO, P. and PAAVOLA, J. (2025) Household flood resilience in the Nowshera district, Pakistan: A multidimensional analysis. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 116, [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2024.105124.
- HOLLING, C.S. (1973) Resilience and Stability of Ecological Systems. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 4(1), pp. 1–23.
- HONG, T. et al. (2023) Ten questions concerning thermal resilience of buildings and occupants for climate adaptation. *Building and Environment*, 244, [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110806.
- IPCC (2023) Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 3–34.
- JRC (2021) *Buildings renovation: data supporting investment measures*. [Online] https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/jrc-news-and-updates/buildings-renovation-data-supporting-investment-measures-2021-02-19_en.
- VAN DE LINDT, J.W., WANG, L. and VAN DE LINDT, J. (2020) Effect of Building Wind-Retrofit Strategies on Socio-economic Community-Level Resilience Metrics Effect of Building Wind-Retrofit Strategies on Socio-economic Community-Level Resilience Metrics Conclusions Community Resilience Model Setup. [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24270.18246.
- MAINALI, B. et al. (2018) Evaluating synergies and trade-offs among Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Explorative analyses of development paths in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(3), [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.3390/su10030815.
- MANES, M., LANGE, D. and RUSH, D. (2023) Resilience, fire and the UK Codes and Standards. Where are they and where could they go? *Indoor and Built Environment*, 32(1), pp. 44–65.
- MIGUEZ, M.G., RAUPP, I.P. and VERÓL, A.P. (2019) An integrated quantitative framework to support design of resilient alternatives to manage urban flood risks. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 12, [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12514.
- MIŠKIĆ, M., ČORIĆ, G. and VUKOSAVLJEVIĆ, D. (2017) Building financial and insurance resilience in the context of climate change. *Economics of Agriculture*, 3(64), pp. 1019–1033.
- MISKIC, M., CORIC, G. and VUKOSAVLJEVIC, D. (2017) Building financial and insurance resilience in the context of climate change. *Ekonomika poljoprivrede*, 64(3), pp. 1019–1033.
- MORSHED, T. and MOURSHED, M. (2023) Overheating and energy use in urban office buildings in a warming climate. *Japan Architectural Review*, 6(1), [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1002/2475-8876.12307.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

- NOFAL, O.M. et al. (2023) Multi-hazard socio-physical resilience assessment of hurricane-induced hazards on coastal communities. *Resilient Cities and Structures*, 2(2), pp. 67–81.
- PSOMAS, T. et al. (2016) Overheating risk barriers to energy renovations of single family houses: Multicriteria analysis and assessment. *Energy and Buildings*, 117, pp. 138–148.
- EUROPEAN UNION (2023) *EU-Level Technical Guidance On Adapting Buildings To Climate Change Action*.
- VAN DE SCHOOT, R. et al. (2021) An open source machine learning framework for efficient and transparent systematic reviews. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 3(2), pp. 125–133.
- STAMATOPOULOS, E. et al. (2024) An adaptive framework for assessing climate resilience in buildings. *Building and Environment*, 264, [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111869.
- UN ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME & GLOBAL ALLIANCE FOR BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTION (2025) *Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction 2024/25*.
- UNDRR (2015) *Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015 - 2030*.
- WEITZ, N. et al. (2018) Towards systemic and contextual priority setting for implementing the 2030 agenda. *Sustainability Science*, 13(2), pp. 531–548.
- ZHANG, Y. et al. (2023) Fire Safety Resilience Assessment of Residential Self-Built Houses according to the TOPSIS Method. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(16), [Online] Available from: doi.org/10.3390/su151612417.

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Annex 1

Table A1: Detailed list of the 31 Resilience Indicators

ID	Indicator Name	Definition	Units	Primary Building Element	Hazard Domain(s)	Rating Method
I01	Structural Fire Resistance Rating (FRR)	Duration structural elements can withstand fire before losing load-bearing capacity.	Minutes	Structural frame, load-bearing walls	Fire	Low: Structure fails quickly in fire (<30 min). Medium: Holds up for about 1 hour. High: Can withstand prolonged fire (≥120 min).
I02	Active Fire Protection System Coverage	Extent of installed systems for detecting and suppressing fire.	N/A	Fire safety systems (detectors, alarms, sprinklers)	Fire	None: No protection systems. Basic: Only extinguishers and smoke detectors. Enhanced: Adds sprinklers. Comprehensive: Fully automated suppression and detection.
I03	Wall Assembly Rating	Thermal resistance and multi-hazard performance of wall systems.	m ² ·K/W	External wall assembly	Thermal, Energy, Fire, Wind, Flood	Very Low: Uninsulated masonry with poor performance. Moderate: Timber/gypsum with some insulation. High: Insulated masonry with good protection. Very High: Advanced reinforced or SIP walls with excellent insulation.
I04	In-Wall Insulation	Effectiveness of wall insulation in resisting heat transfer.	m ² ·K/W	Wall insulation	Thermal, Energy	None: No insulation. Basic: Fibreglass batts (moderate). Improved: Cellulose or spray foam (good). Advanced: Aerogel or equivalent (very high).
I05	Window-to-Wall Ratio (WWR)	Ratio of total window area to wall area, influencing energy demand and structural exposure.	%	External façade	Thermal, Energy, Wind	Low: Small window area (<20%), energy efficient but limited daylight. Medium: Balanced window area (20–40%). High: Large window area (>40%), more daylight but less energy efficient.
I06	Window Glazing Energy–Impact Rating	Thermal efficiency and impact resistance of glazing systems.	W/m ² ·K (U-value)	Windows and glazing	Thermal, Energy, Wind	Low: Single-pane glass, poor insulation. Medium: Standard double-pane glass. High: Triple-pane with coatings, very efficient.

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						Very High: Advanced laminated or dynamic glazing.
I07	External Shutter & Impact Protection	Measures presence and robustness of external protective shutters.	N/A	Windows, external doors	Wind, Fire	None: No shutters. Temporary: Basic plywood/cardboard. Semi-permanent: Accordion shutters. Permanent: Roll-down or storm shutters. Advanced: Specialized hurricane or fire shutters.
I08	Ventilation System & Air Change Rate	Capacity of ventilation system to provide airflow and smoke control.	ACH	Ventilation/HVAC	Thermal, Fire	Low: Natural ventilation only (≤ 3 ACH). Medium: Mixed natural and mechanical (3–6 ACH). High: Full mechanical with filtration and smoke control (>6 ACH).
I09	Stormwater–Sewer Separation	Presence of separated stormwater and wastewater systems.	N/A	Drainage system	Flood	Low: Combined sewer system (higher flood risk). High: Fully separated stormwater and wastewater network.
I10	Drainage Network Capacity for Extreme Rainfall	Design capacity of drainage systems to handle extreme rainfall.	L/s	Stormwater drainage	Flood	Low: Designed for minor storms (<10 -year). High: Designed for severe storms (≥ 50 -year) including climate change allowance.
I11	Backup Power Autonomy for Critical Loads	Duration critical systems can operate during power outages.	Hours	Backup power system	Energy, Fire, Flood	None: No backup. Short: Up to 4 hours for essentials. Medium: Around 1 day for critical needs. High: Whole-building backup for extended outages.
I12	Flood-Safe Placement of Plumbing Fixtures	Elevation of plumbing fixtures relative to flood design levels.	N/A	Plumbing system	Flood	Low: Fixtures located below flood level. High: Fixtures installed above flood design level.
I13	Indoor Overheating Degree (IOD)	Extent of overheating indoors relative to comfort thresholds.	$^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{hours}/\text{year}$	Indoor environment	Thermal	High resilience: Rare overheating ($\leq 50^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}/\text{year}$). Medium: Moderate overheating (51–200). Low: Frequent overheating (>200).
I14	Specific Energy Use for	Annual energy required for heating and cooling per floor area.	$\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{year}$	Energy system	Energy	High: Very efficient (≤ 40 $\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{year}$). Medium: Moderate efficiency (41–80). Low: High consumption (>80).

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Heating & Cooling						
I15	Unmet Degree Hours (UDH) for Thermal Comfort	Hours when indoor temperature deviates from comfort range.	°C·hours/year	Indoor environment	Thermal	High: Comfortable most of the time (≤ 100 h/year outside comfort). Medium: Moderate discomfort (101–300). Low: Frequent discomfort (>300).
I16	Structural Anchoring & Connection Compliance	Compliance of anchoring and structural connections with codes.	N/A	Structural frame	Wind	None: No compliance. Partial: Some compliance with standards. Full: Meets building code. Enhanced: Exceeds standard with hurricane/seismic resistance.
I17	Ground Floor Opening-to-Wall Ratio	Proportion of openings in ground-floor walls affecting vulnerability.	%	External façade	Flood, Wind	High resilience: Few openings ($\leq 20\%$). Medium: Moderate openings (21–50%). Low: Many openings ($>50\%$).
I18	Roof Assembly Multi-Hazard Resistance	Roof's performance against multiple hazards and insulation quality.	N/A	Roof system	Thermal, Wind, Fire	None: No insulation or resistance. Poor: Low-quality asphalt. Moderate: Insulated asphalt. High: Insulated metal or cool/green roof. Very High: Hurricane-resistant roof.
I19	Exterior Door Fire–Flood–Wind Resistance	Door rating against fire, water penetration, and wind loads.	N/A	Exterior doors	Flood, Fire, Wind	High: Rated doors that resist fire, flood, and wind. Low: Standard doors with limited resistance.
I20	Elevation of Lowest Occupied Floor	Height of lowest occupied floor above flood design level.	Metres	Floor system	Flood	High: ≥ 1 m above flood level. Medium: 0.6–0.99 m. Low: <0.6 m.
I21	Plinth/Base Level Elevation	Elevation of plinth or base level above ground or flood line.	Metres	Foundation	Flood	High: ≥ 0.6 m above ground/flood. Low: <0.6 m.
I22	Foundation Type & Hazard Resistance	Foundation system type and its resistance to hazards.	N/A	Foundation	Flood, Wind	Low: Slab-on-grade, vulnerable to floods/wind. High: Elevated piles or piers, hazard resistant.

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I23	Floodwater Removal System Capacity	Capacity of installed systems to remove floodwater.	L/s	Drainage system	Flood	Low: <20 L/s. Medium: 20–50 L/s. High: ≥50 L/s.
I24	External Envelope Floodproofing Coverage	Extent of floodproofing applied to walls and envelope.	%	External envelope	Flood	Low: Less than half floodproofed. Medium: 50–90% protected. High: Nearly fully protected (>90%).
I25	Roof Geometry & Shape Performance	Aerodynamic and thermal performance of roof shape.	N/A	Roof	Wind, Thermal	High: Hip or hexagonal roofs, best for wind and heat. Medium: Gable roofs, moderate. Low: Flat roofs, poor performance.
I26	Roof Pitch Angle	Steepness of roof slope affecting wind and thermal performance.	Degrees or % slope	Roof	Wind, Thermal	Optimal: 30–45°. Low: Too flat (<15°).
I27	Roof Overhang Length for Shading & Rain Protection	Length of roof overhang providing shading and rain protection.	Metres	Roof	Thermal, Flood	High: Long overhangs (≥0.6 m) for shading and rain protection. Low: Short overhangs (<0.3 m).
I28	Primary Structural System Type	Material and reinforcement of primary structural system.	N/A	Structural frame	Wind, Fire	Low: Non-reinforced materials. High: Reinforced concrete or steel.
I29	Wall Lateral Load Resistance Capacity	Wall strength against lateral wind loads.	kN/m	Walls	Wind	High: Strong walls (≥10 kN/m). Low: Weak walls (<5 kN/m).
I30	Gutter Guard & Debris Protection Coverage	Extent of gutter protection against clogging by debris.	%	Roof drainage	Flood	Low: Minimal coverage (<50%). High: Nearly complete coverage (>90%).

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I31	Defensible Space for fire Protection	Distance of cleared vegetation or buffers around the building.	Metres	Site surroundings	Fire	Low: Narrow clearance (<10 m). High: Wide buffer zone (≥ 30 m).
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Table A2: Populated CIM with the relation of the indicators

	I01	I02	I03	I04	I05	I06	I07	I08	I09	I10	I11	I12	I13	I14	I15	I16	I17	I18	I19	I20	I21	I22	I23	I24	I25	I26	I27	I28	I29	I30	I31	
I01	0	+1	+1	0	-1	-1	+1	0	N	N	0	N	N	N	N	+1	-1	+1	+1	N	N	0	N	N	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	
I02	+1	0	0	0	-1	-1	+1	0	N	N	+1	N	N	0	N	0	-1	+1	+1	N	N	0	N	N	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	
I03	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N	N	N	0	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	N	0	0	N	0	0	0	0	0	N	N	N	
I04	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	N	N	+1	N	-1	+1	+1	N	0	0	0	N	N	N	N	N	0	N	N	N	N	N	N	
I05	-1	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	+1	N	N	N	N	-1	-1	-1	N	+1	N	N	N	N	N	N	-1	N	N	0	0	-1	N	N	
I06	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	N	N	0	N	+1	+1	+1	N	+1	+1	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
I07	+1	+1	0	0	+1	+1	0	0	0	N	0	N	+1	+1	-1	0	0	0	+1	0	N	N	0	0	0	N	+1	0	N	N	+1	
I08	0	0	0	0	0	0	N	0	N	N	+1	0	-1	+1	+1	N	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	0	0	N	-1	
I09	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	0	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	0	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
I10	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	0	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
I11	0	+1	N	0	N	0	N	+1	0	0	0	N	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	0	0	0	N	0	N	N	0	
I12	N	N	0	N	0	N	N	0	0	0	N	0	N	N	N	N	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N	0	0	N	
I13	N	N	0	0	0	0	N	-1	0	0	-1	N	0	+1	+1	N	+1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	N	N	-1	-1	-1	-1	N	N	0	
I14	N	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	N	-1	0	+1	N	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	N	N	-1	-1	-1	-1	N	N	-1	
I15	N	N	0	0	0	0	-1	+1	0	0	-1	N	+1	-1	0	N	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	N	N	-1	-1	-1	-1	N	N	-1	
I16	+1	0	0	N	0	0	0	N	0	0	0	N	N	N	N	0	-1	+1	-1	+1	+1	+1	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	-1	+1	N	N	
I17	-1	-1	0	-1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	-1	0	0	+1	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	+1	+1	-1	N	0	
I18	+1	+1	0	+1	N	0	0	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	+1	+1	
I19	+1	+1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	-1	+1	0	0	+1	+1	0	+1	+1	0	0	+1	0	-1	N	0	
I20	N	N	0	0	N	0	0	0	+1	+1	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	+1	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	0	0	
I21	N	N	0	0	0	0	N	0	+1	+1	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	+1	+1	0	+1	+1	+1	0	0	+1	+1	0	0	0	
I22	0	0	0	0	N	N	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	+1	+1	0	0	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	N	0
I23	N	N	0	+1	N	0	N	0	+1	+1	+1	0	N	N	N	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	+1	N	
I24	N	N	+1	+1	0	N	0	0	+1	+1	0	0	N	N	N	+1	-1	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	+1	0	+1	+1	+1	0	0	+1	0	
I25	+1	+1	0	+1	0	N	0	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	0	+1	+1	N	0	+1	+1	
I26	0	0	0	0	0	N	N	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	+1	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	0	+1	0	0	+1	0	
I27	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	N	N	+1	+1	+1	-1	+1	+1	+1	0	+1	0	+1	N	+1	+1	0	0	N	0	N	
I28	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	+1	+1	0	0	N	0	0	0	+1	N	N	
I29	0	0	N	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N	0	N	N	N	+1	-1	0	-1	+1	0	+1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N	N	
I30	+1	+1	+1	+1	N	0	N	N	0	0	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	+1	N	0	0	N	+1	+1	+1	+1	N	N	N	0	N	
I31	+1	+1	+1	+1	+1	+1	0	0	0	0	0	N	0	+1	0	N	0	+1	0	0	0	0	N	+1	+1	0	-1	0	N	+1	0	